

Taiping jing

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Text, Early Chinese text, Religious Group

The Taiping jing was compiled in the late 6th century by Daoist practitioners who were close to the Upper Clarity (shangqing 上清) group whose basis was at Mount Mao (Maoshan 茅山), in Jurong County 句容市 of Jiangsu Province. Due to linguistic and doctrinal reasons, most scholars agree it originated in the late second century CE. It consists of roughly three textual layers. The bulk, layer A, is an account of meetings between a heaven-sent Celestial Master (tianshi 天師) and a group of at least six students who have travelled from elsewhere to be instructed. They discuss the urgent need to actively promote universal great peace so as to prevent the approaching cataclysm that threatens the end of humankind and, in consequence, heaven and earth. The main topic is the need for widespread moral reforms. Regarding philosophical intention and terminology, layer A has parallels in Han dynasty (206 BCE- 220 CE) socio-political thought. Layer B contains conversations between a disciple and members of the celestial bureaucracy who discuss the chances for a career in the celestial bureaucracy. The disciple aims to turn immortal, which became the primary content of Daoist religious instruction. Layer C contains religious materials, in the form of talismans (fu 符) or reiterated characters (fuwen 複文), images and short Upper Clarity passages; it also includes a brief summary of layer A; several sections, composed in layer A style, propose positions divergent from those expressed in layer A. The 6th-century text was organised in ten divisions (bu 部), 170 chapters (juan 卷) and 366 sections. Simultaneous to the compilation, it was accepted into the Daoist Canon (Daozang 道藏). Due to the Canon's spurious transmission, parts of the Taiping jing were lost so that the text we have today has 57 chapters. It relies on the Canon that was printed in 1445. A manuscript preserved in Dunhuang (S 4226) contains the full table of contents of the 6th-century text. The 9th-century Taiping jing chao (Digest of the Taiping jing 太平經鈔), in ten divisions, consists of excerpts from the full 6th-century text. We can draw conclusions from these two sources regarding parts of the 6th-century text that have not been transmitted. For the four hundred years between the supposed origin of much of the Taiping jing and the creation of the transmitted text, there is hardly any evidence for the text's existence. Throughout the Han dynasty, the term great peace was widely used. Historical sources mention that in the outgoing first century BCE and again in the mid-second century CE, texts with great peace in their title were presented to emperors but did not find acceptance. These texts may have had some impact. Whether the second one, titled Taiping qingling shu (Book on great peace with the title written in blue 太平清領書), played a role in the Yellow Turban rebellion of 184 CE is under debate. The Yellow Turbans were originally the Great Peace Movement (Taiping dao 太平道) that had started well over a decade earlier. Daoist hagiographic sources, followed by a number of scholars, depict the second of these texts on great peace as the original version of the Taiping jing that entered the Daoist Canon. It was written by Gan Ji 干吉, an expert in vitality techniques (fangshi 方士) in the region of Langya 琅琊 in the southeast of today's Shandong province and presented to Emperors Shun 順 (r. 125-144) and Huan 桓 (r. 147-168). In 166 BCE, the scholar-official Xiang Kai 襄楷 travelled from Langya to the court to present the text and two memorials in its praise that official historical accounts have preserved. While there is no way to prove any material link between the Taiping qingling shu and the received Taiping jing, it is not impossible that layer A and layer B materials of the received text originated in the environment and at the time when Gan Ji and Xiang Kai were active.

Date Range: 150 CE - 2022 CE

Region: People's Republic of China

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

Borders of present-day China

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 2: Yu Liming 俞理明, *Taiping jing zhengdu 太平經正讀*. Chengdu: Ba Shu shushe, 2001.

Notes: This edition corrects errors of Wang Ming's edition , fills in lacunas and adds linguistic explanations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

– Source 3: Yang Jilin 楊寄林, ed. *Taiping jing 太平經*. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2013.

Notes: This edition is critical and contains extensive explanations and a thoughtful Baihua translation of the whole text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

– Source 1: Wang Ming 王明, *Taiping jing hejiao 太平經合校*. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju,

Notes: This is a punctuated edition that integrates the text of the *Taiping jing chao* (Daozang no 1101.b) into that of the *Taiping jing* (Daozang no 1101.a). Other new editions of the *Taiping jing* follow this model with the exception of: *Taiping jing*, Shanghai: Guji chubanshe, 1993, editor unknown. This title is a punctuated edition of the original Daozang versions of the *Taiping jing chao* and the *Taiping jing*, kept separately.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: www.chant.org

– Source 1 Description: The Chinese Ancient Text Database (CHANT) is a scholarly website that contains a complete copy of the *Taiping jing* and *Taiping jing chao* 鈔. It usually follows Wang Ming's edition. It is searchable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1445 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Beijing and Shanghai

Number of sheets

– Bound

Notes: The received text has been transmitted in the Daoist canon titled Zhengtong daozeang 正統道藏 printed in 1445 in the capital Beijing. In 1926 the Commercial Press in Shanghai produced the first version of the Daoist canon in movable type printing. In this canon the Taiping jing consists of eight fascicles (no 748-755); the Taiping jing chao of two (no 746-747).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1445 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Beijing and Shanghai

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 1119 CE

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 1119 CE

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

– Impressed

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1100 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Fujian

Tool for making the impression(s)

– Other [specify]: Woodblocks

Notes: The Zhenghe Wanshou Daozang 政和萬壽道藏, finished in 1119 CE, included the first printed edition of the Taiping jing. No relics have been preserved. It was produced at Mount Jiuxian 九仙山 in Fujian province; stored in the capital Kaifeng, Henan province and probably empire wide.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1100 CE - 1119 CE

Region: Fujian

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Wood

Notes: Bamboo or wooden slips, size for instance 21 x 0.8 cm. This entry is constructed on the basis of general knowledge about the materiality of texts in the second century CE and on the fact that from analyzing the received text of the Taiping jing scholars conclude that it was in part written in that period. There is no archaeological or other evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 220 CE

Region: Shandong

Species

– Specify: Unknown

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 220 CE

Region: Shandong

– Bamboo

Notes: Bamboo or wooden slips, size for instance 21 x 0.8 cm. This entry is constructed on the basis of general knowledge about the materiality of texts in the second century CE and on the fact that from analyzing the received text of the Taiping jing scholars conclude that it was in part written in that period. There is no archaeological or other evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 220 CE

Region: Shandong

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 1119 CE

Region: Shandong

Specify type of paper

– Specify: In the second century CE paper may have consisted of bamboo fibers and the inner bark of a mulberry tree.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 100 CE - 200 CE

Region: Shandong

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: Wooden and bamboo slips needed physical preparation. Corrections did occur. There was no ritual preparation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 220 CE

Region: Shandong

– Corrections

Notes: Wooden and bamboo slips needed physical preparation. Corrections did occur. There was no ritual preparation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 220 CE

Region: Shandong

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The writing of the text was not a process of copying. It was the fixation of what had before been oral communication. This at least is the impression one derives from reading the received text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 600 CE

Region: Shandong

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– Yes

Notes: Once edited in the 6th century the text was, we must assume, stored in Daoist temples and monasteries. Once printed, the text was stored in the imperial library and in Daoist monasteries. The version that was the basis for the modern edition of 1926 was stored in Beijing in the Baiyun guan 白雲觀 White Cloud Monastery.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1119 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: The Daojing taiping bu jian dier (Second Chapter of the Great Peace Division of Daoist Scriptures 道經太平部卷第二), S 4226, has been preserved in cave 17, the so-called “Library cave”, of the Buddhist Mogao Caves in Dunhuang 敦煌 in Gansu province, written on paper in the early 7th century CE. It provides a table of contents of the Taiping jing in 366 jian as it was edited in the 6th century, i.e. of the received text. The manuscript contains praise for the Taiping jing's teachings, several quotations and tells a version of the Daoist saga of the text's origin. At present, the manuscript is stored in the British Library in London as part of the Aurel Stein collection.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Daoist practitioners kept early texts on great peace in their libraries. This is certified by the Daoist writer and practitioner Ge Hong 葛洪 (283-343).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 200 CE - 400 CE

Region: Jiangsu

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: The received text was stored in imperial libraries and the libraries of Daoist monasteries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Specify

– Specify: No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

Notes: The north wall of Cave 17 of the Mogao Caves in Dunhuang is decorated. The iconography is in no way related to the text. A sculpture of the Buddhist monk Hong Bian is situated next to the wall.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

Notes: The iconography is Buddhist

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The fresco depicts two figures and trees. The meaning is unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Gansu

↳ Humans
– Yes
Notes: wooden sculpture of a monk
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE
Region: Gansu

↳ Supernatural narratives
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE
Region: Gansu

↳ Human narratives
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE
Region: Gansu

↳ Specify
– Specify: No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE
Region: Gansu

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1000 CE - 1300 CE
Region: Gansu

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: If for the Han dynasty origins we follow the Daoist saga the text's initiator gained his livelihood from services to the community and teaching. Students helped finalizing and propagating these teachings. The 6th century edition was supported by the Daoist Upper Clarity lineage and by the emperors of the Liang 梁 (502-557) and Chen 陳 (557-589) dynasties. The compiler and editor Zhou Zhixiang 周智響 and his predecessor Huan Kai 桓闡 were both Upper Clarity Daoists. Zhou Zhixiang submitted his work to Emperor Xuan 宣 (r. 569-582). Shortly afterwards the Taiping jing became part of the Daozang and was since then reproduced by copyists and later engravers employed by the imperial court.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Copyists and engravers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: Certain religious officials were aligned to the bureaucratic apparatus that supervised religious affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: No, not for the religious text in question.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Notes: No, not from the religious text in question.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping jing was kept and preserved by members of Daoist lineages. These men and women were often freed from paying taxes and providing labour services.

↳ Production

– Yes

Notes: Not for the production of the text in Han dynasty. The compiler and editor of the 6th century text had the Emperor's support.

↳ Storage

– Yes

Notes: Monasteries were tax-exempt and received imperial funds for building projects and maintenance. The maintenance of their libraries was of public interest.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Study

– Yes

Notes: Zhou Zhixiang had imperial support for editing the received text and teaching classes on its contents. In honour of the Daoist Chu Boyu 褚伯玉 (394-479) who according to Daoist sources studied a scripture on great peace the first emperor of the Qi 齊 (479-502) dynasty set up a Great Peace Monastery. We do not know whether Chu Boyu's studies were related to materials that were integrated in the received text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 450 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Jiangsu

↳ Specify

–Specify: Not applicable

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Present full-time?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Present part-time?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: They are male. Female religious specialists had other tasks

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Fujian

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: For religious specialists who were monks. Many were not.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE

Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: While there are formal institutions there are also alternative ways of training.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 550 CE - 1445 CE
Region: Jiangsu, Fujian, and Beijing

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: It is part of the Daoist canon (Daozang).

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Notes: This entry relies on the Daoist saga of the text's origin. An alternative story is told by the text. The Taiping jing describes students who record in writing the Celestial Master's lectures and the dialogues between Master and students. Much of layer A of the received text is written as if it were lecture notes.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE
Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: The high god is Laozi. Daoist sources contain different stories on how Gan Ji received the text. One version, reported in the Santian neijie jing (Scripture of the Inner Explanations of the Three Heavens 三天内解經) proposes that in the fourth to third century BCE Laozi in one of his transformations bestowed the text on Ganji in Langya.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE
Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

Notes: The Shenxian zhuan (神仙傳 Biographies of immortals) has the story that in Beihai 北海 (Northern Shandong) the immortal and fangshi Bo He 帛和 appeared as a

medicine seller and gave the text to Gan Ji.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE

Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE

Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE

Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: Laozi is divine. Immortals like Bo He and Gan Ji the Daoist tradition may call semi-divine. The term sounds almost Eurocentric and therefore hard to apply in a Daoist context.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE

Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 BCE - 150 CE

Region: Region north of the Yellow River

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 150 CE - 600 CE

↳ |

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– No

Notes: In practice, scriptures were frequently altered. Theoretically, they were revealed and standard.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Codification began in the 5th century. The Taiping jing became part of the canon in the

early 7th century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 400 CE - 2022 CE

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 100000000

Notes: This number is for the population of the Song dynasty (960-1276). The intended audience was the whole population of China at any given time.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 960 CE - 1276 CE

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 100000000

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 960 CE - 1276 CE

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 1

Notes: This number is a placeholder only, there is no known smallest audience.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 1400000000

Notes: The Taiping jing, like many Daoist texts is addressed to everyone.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2015 CE - 2022 CE

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: The intended audience changed with changes in the population. The actual audience increased with the availability of printed copies and the increase in literacy. After the Daoist canon had been printed the Taiping jing was at times quoted in anthologies. There is no evidence of a wide readership.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– I don't know

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These options do not apply. The audience was in no way restricted .

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: I understand missionary work as approaching people of different ethnic backgrounds. The text mentions them and for another early Daoist movement we know that it integrated them.

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The text is read by individuals, as one would read a book. The "ritual practice" is the individual perusal of the text.

↳ Is it orally recited?

– No

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The answers to this question rely on how the text's impact on its audience is described in the text.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: It is argued in the text that by reciting or reading it people will be healthy, happy and live long.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The "ritual practice" is the individual perusal of the text.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– No

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Notes: This question does not apply because the text is not used in ritual practice outside of the act of reading it. However, the text depicts talks between Master and students. When students err as is often the case the Master corrects them.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Notes: This question does not apply because the text is not used in ritual practice outside of the act of reading it. The student's conduct is a topic of the talks between Master and students.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

Notes: This question does not apply because the text is not used in ritual practice outside of the act of reading it.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

Notes: In traditional China all texts had material significance. The answers provided for the following questions are based on this general point and on isolated passages in the text.

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– Yes

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Yes

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is the knowledge hidden?

– No

↳ Is the knowledge occult?

– No

↳ Is the knowledge esoteric?

– Yes

↳ Other type of knowledge?

–Specify: The text provides moral guidelines.

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Yes

↳ Physical healing

– Yes

↳ Mental/psychological healing

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– Yes

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, necessarily.

↳ Specify

– Specify: It was initially written on wooden slips, bamboo slips or paper and is now read as a printed volume

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: Daoist talismans or reiterated characters can be called calligraphic.

↳ Illustrations?

– Yes

Notes: Drawings of immortals.

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: However, as time went by the text was shrinking. The Daoist canon it was part of underwent many changes. The text had 170 chapters in the 6th century and by 1445 only 57 chapters were left.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: By including the text in the official canon. The decision lay with leading priests and court officials.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: Between the 7th century and 1445 the canon's contents changed frequently. Also, several additions to the canon printed in 1445 have been published.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 2022 CE

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text consists of several layers. One layer is in the tradition of a dialogue between teacher and students that started with Confucius' Analects and has remained a literary tradition.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Socio-political implications

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text includes none of these.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: However, the text does advocate for official employment with a regular income, reforms of mortuary rituals, rules for earth works, drinking alcoholic beverages, and relations between teacher and student. It also condemns female infanticide and suggests rules for sexual intercourse.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit-mind is meant to be the body's ruler.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: Calmness

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: Debates cover the need for the spirit-mind to stay in control.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: The debate includes the concept of spirits who reside in the body.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: "Reincarnation" is the wrong term. Someone turned immortal retains their personality. They are present in heaven and at times on earth, in various functions.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text argues that the service to the dead, which includes funerary rituals must not exceed the service they received while alive. Funerary rituals must be modest. One must use geomantic methods for choosing the appropriate burial site. Ancestors buried in the wrong soil will harm descendants.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The "Supreme High God" is heaven (tian 天), the same character as that is used for "sky". Its will is continuously referred to as the highest authority there is. One textual layer describes a talk between "Lord of Heaven" (tian jun 天君), who looks as if he were almost omnipotent, a deity of middle rank and an advanced Daoist practitioner (Taiping jing, section 179).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: Not only to elites but to everyone. He is life-giving.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: It is angry or happy; punishes or rewards; is ill or in good health. It is not

omnipotent. It cannot prevent the approaching cataclysm that will also put itself to an end.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– Yes

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: it cares; it feels responsible

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through emissaries and spirits. The high god and all spirits communicate with humans who meditate.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: The text itself, the Master's lectures and study materials he bestowed on students are all expressions of heaven's will. The scripture's ties to heaven are diverse, complex and intensive. Through studying the text, i.e., reading, reciting and copying it, discussing its contents and distributing its message people understand heaven's will, or in other words communicate with heaven.

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: By adhering to the text's moral and behavioral guidelines students remain on good terms with spirits.

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Notes: For special problems, as for instance illness, rituals are of use, and one is described in some detail.

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Insights; awareness of divine agency; vision beyond the five senses. In the main, inspiration is gained by meditation.

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The Celestial Master, the text's main speaker, was human before he became a celestial official and is shown in the text as being present. While other human spirits are hardly mentioned in the Taiping jing the text does not question their existence. They were a general feature of the Han dynasty world view.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: I understand “knowledge” as the ordinary knowledge of an intelligent human.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: Is well educated and relies on past experiences.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– No
Notes: Through meditation.

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Communicate through other means
– Specify: Meditation

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: These evil spirits are in the tradition of spirits that shamanists help to control. Their power is psychic: they give wrong advice, betray and mislead a person so that they get into trouble. Their intention is to rob a person of their Dao. One must learn to ignore what they say.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are evil. Their intention is to harm humans. They know enough to do so. It remains unclear whether they know anything else. These evil spirits are in the tradition of spirits that shamanists help to control. Their power is psychic: they give wrong advice, betray and mislead a person so that they get into trouble. Their intention is to rob a person of their Dao. One must learn to ignore what they say.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - No
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
- ↳ In dreams?
 - No
- ↳ In trance possession?
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

–Specify: anger; meanness; cruelty

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Pantheon may be the wrong word. There is some order and hierarchy but the organizational structure is weak.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: The pantheon is in flux. Heaven and earth are in a dominating position. Others fit in somewhere.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: My background is not in religious studies. I am not sure what is here meant by "divine". Immortals (xian 仙) may have human form and human skills but have, so to speak of, survived their own death and have now access to otherworldly regions. The text's main speaker, the Celestial Master, is such an immortal and his student's main wish is to become one.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: They talk to each other, as would humans. Humans communicate with them through meditation.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are talked to in all layers of the text. I am not sure about the meaning of "physically present". Supernatural beings come into existence in meditation. The practitioner, in the text always male, talks to the figure he envisages as if addressing a person of rank. The Taiping jing provides instruction on life style and meditation techniques that enable a practitioner to envisage a supernatural being. One needs such instruction before being able to communicate with spirits.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: The presence of all beings, be they spirits and supernatural or not, is as ordinary as is the presence of humans.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other form of divination:

- Specify: By use of the calendar; the sexagenary system of stems and branches; iatromantic and geomantic techniques; astronomic observations; astrological principles; revealed writings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Shandong and Jiangsu

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– Yes

Notes: The text only hints at this topic. There are no details.

↳ Food

– No

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: Damage done to earth; killings; disrespect for seasonal demands.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

Notes: A celibate life style is prohibited.

↳ Adultery

– No

↳ Incest

– Yes

Notes: Not mentioned; the taboo was general and therefore accepted, I suppose.

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– No

Notes: Not mentioned; I don't know.

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

Notes: I am not sure what you mean. The text severely condemns economic exploitation, the use of personal social and economic power to the detriment of others and greediness.

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: Sexual intercourse is encouraged.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
Notes: The text demands the distribution of all property.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes

Notes: They argue that everyone should earn his or her living.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The topic is not mentioned

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: They care about supporting widows and orphans and everyone in need; they care about self-cultivation and study; they care about obedience to heaven or the natural order.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Virtually all misadventures can and must be seen as punishment: illness, family problems, business failures in the case of individuals, and natural disasters, epidemics, harvest failures, wars in the case of society as a whole.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

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↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Notes: The term selfishness does not occur. The position could be paraphrased as encouraging altruism.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Done to warn people that their conduct will lead to the great cataclysm or apocalypse that will end all.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

– Specify: To be installed as an official in the inferior realm in charge of inflicting punishments.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: Early, untimely death

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Notes: Again: the term does not occur. There is a demand for self-cultivation; to neglect oneself is a crime. What is encouraged is altruism.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

Notes: Career as a celestial official

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Longevity is the main reward.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: Some scholars call the Celestial Master who as heaven's spokesperson initiates reforms that are supposed to lead humans to a new cooperation with heaven a saviour or messiah. They may have a point, although as a process salvation relies on the population in general who implement these reforms.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text's answers are slightly contradictory. All that can be said is in the entries that follow. They are mainly based on the text's Celestial Master layer, where eschatological issues are a topic. As opposed to other early Daoist texts, the authors of the Taiping jing assume that an apocalyptic end can be prevented by activating society as a whole. Should this not work out, the end would be universal. Should it work out, everyone and everything would be saved. The idea expressed in other Daoist texts that only Daoist community members will survive the apocalypse is not put forth in the Taiping jing.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: This is not mentioned but is in principle possible since the eschaton results from the load of trespasses humans have accumulated. This load is so big that the eschaton is to happen now, if not prevented. Once prevented another load could be accumulated. However, this is a construction for which I did not find any evidence anywhere in the received text. The text argues that once great peace has been established and thereby the eschaton prevented, it will last for myriads and myriads of years.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: They need to perform specific tasks to prevent the World's end.

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

Notes: The cataclysm results from the damage done to the cosmic equilibrium. It can be called the natural result of human conduct. The existence of the "High God", that is heaven, will also come to an end.

↳ Restoration of the world

– Yes

Notes: This is possible when humans change their conduct.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: There is no need for a system change.

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Notes: The aim is to reactivate the existing system.

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: The text understands the approaching end as resulting from the load of human trespasses against the cosmic equilibrium that humans have accumulated through history. At present a new beginning is possible.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– I don't know

Notes: The text consists of several layers, and each layer may come from different sources. Therefore, the text gives several answers: the approaching end can be prevented; if not, nobody will survive; should there be an end, a new beginning would be possible.

– Yes

Notes: The text consists of several layers, and each layer may come from different sources. Therefore, the text gives several answers: the approaching end can be prevented; if not, nobody will survive; should there be an end, a new beginning would be possible.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

Notes: I answer this question following the text's main line that suggests people will rapidly change and prevent the cataclysm. There are other lines.

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: Life style changes must be implemented now, by everyone, in order to avoid the eschaton. If not, no one will survive.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
 - No

- ↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
 - All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
 - Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - No

- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - No

- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - No

- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes

Notes: I have problems with the term selflessness. Giving for instance is not seen as selfless but in one's interest. One looks after oneself by following the rules, and the rule is to give to those in need. This can be interpreted as selflessness but is not formulated as such.

- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes

- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: This topic is hardly ever mentioned although a practitioner's life style is at times ascetic.
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
 - Notes: In dealing with one's superior and one's teacher
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
 - Notes: This point is central.
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Communality

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Different textual layers have different positions. The layer interested in the arrival of great peace does not deal with fasting. The layer that deals with a practitioner who is about to turn immortal describes that fasting has so weakened him that co-religionists must look after him.

– Yes

Notes: Different textual layers have different positions. The layer interested in the arrival of great peace does not deal with fasting. The layer that deals with a practitioner who is about to turn immortal describes that fasting has so weakened him that co-religionists must look after him.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: There is the need for study, study meetings, discussions and proselytizing in the textual layer interested in great peace. The practitioner who wants to turn immortal must change his psychological and to some extent physical being before he will succeed. These practices are very time consuming.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: The text addresses people who are householders with duties regarding family and ancestors. There are no details but practitioners are within limits meant to be sociable.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: I am not sure about the meaning of “institutionalized”. The text demands that relief and care is organized by the community at hand. Its size and administrative level are usually left vague.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: teaching; healing; spreading information

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text suggests the foundation of an academy that would train officials to communicate between heaven and the political ruler.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Notes: This is done in an indirect manner: Everyone is expected to learn how to study texts.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The education of girls and women is not mentioned. However, they are supposed to participate in discussion groups and to have a say. The text often says that the people must study. This term includes everyone.

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Chinese education was gendered. The students whom the text depicts as learning from the Celestial Master are probably all male. Their sex is not mentioned.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: 1:6 is given at several occasions. The number of students could also be bigger.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Students may learn from different masters. They are not supposed to say “thank you” to their teacher since their obligation is too big to be covered by such a word.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: One may become an official in this world. One may also become a celestial official.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: It argues that wars must be avoided.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Small-scale agriculture/horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: This is often mentioned since it dominates people's life. The text does not know of ritual food production